

Synthesis and Biological Activities of Certain Derivatives of 3-Aryl-4(3H)-Quinazolinones. Part—I

CH. RAVI SHANKAR, A. DEVENDAR RAO, E. JAYASENA REDDY and V. MALLA REDDY*

University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 2 April 1982, accepted 12 November 1982

Nine different 3-aryl-2-(N',N'-substituted aminomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones have been synthesized by condensing 3-aryl-2-chloromethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones with different secondary bases. Similarly, seven different 3-aryl-2-(N⁴-arylsulphonamidomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones have been obtained on reacting 3-aryl-2-chloromethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones with various aryl sulphonamides. These compounds have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data. The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the compounds have been determined and the results are discussed.

4-QUINAZOLINONES have been reported to possess antibacterial and antiviral properties¹.

Some 2-alkyl-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones have been shown to possess bactericidal as well as tuberculostatic activities²⁻⁴. 3-(p-Alkoxyphenyl)-2-isomylthio-4(3H)-quinazolinone derivatives have been reported as most active against *M. tuberculosis*⁵. 3-Aryl-2-[D-threo-(-)-l-(p-nitrophenyl)-1,3-dihydroxy-2-propylamino]-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones have also been found to exert bacteriostatic effect similar to sulphanilamide⁶. Recently Abdel-Aleem and Abdel-Ghafer⁷ have reported the synthesis and bactericidal activity of certain 3-aryl-2-(β-arylsulphonylhydrazinomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones. Pandey and Agarwal⁸ have reported the synthesis and antiviral activity of some morpholino/diethylamino-dithiocarbamyl-methyl-3(aryl substituted)-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones.

In view of the interesting biological and pharmacological activities of various quinazolinone derivatives, the syntheses of 3-aryl-2-(N',N'-substituted aminomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones and 3-aryl-2-(N⁴-aryl sulphonamidomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones and their screening for such properties have been taken up. The synthesis of the present quinazolinone derivatives has been outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

* Author for correspondence.

3-Aryl-2-chloromethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones (III) were synthesized⁹ by condensation of N-chloroacetyl anthranilic acid (I) with appropriate aromatic amines in presence of PCl₃. Their melting points comply with those reported¹⁰. Compound III on reacting with a secondary amine in presence of pyridine or toluene yielded the corresponding 3-aryl-2-(N',N'-substituted aminomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (IV). Relatively higher yields were obtained when the reaction was conducted in toluene.

Compound III on reaction with aryl sulphonamides under similar conditions yielded 3-aryl-2-(N⁴-aryl sulphonamidomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (V).

The compounds IV and V have been purified by column chromatography and characterised by their analytical and spectral data.

All the compounds have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal properties by standard methods^{11,12}.

Experimental

The purity of the compounds has been checked by tlc. Melting points have been determined in sulphuric acid-bath and are uncorrected. The ir spectra of the compounds have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord-283 spectrophotometer by preparing KBr discs. The uv spectra have been recorded on Shimadzu MPS-5000 spectrophotometer. The physical and analytical data are presented in Table 1.

General procedure for the syntheses of 3-aryl-2-(N',N'-substituted aminomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (IV) and 3-aryl-2-(N⁴-aryl sulphonamidomethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (V): A mixture of 3-aryl-2-chloromethyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (III, 0.01 mol) and appropriate secondary base/aryl sulphonamide (0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. Pyridine was distilled off as far as possible and the residue was poured on crushed ice with constant

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF DERIVATIVES OF 3-ARYL-4(3H)-QUINAZOLINONES

Sl. No.	Compd. No.	Ar	R ¹ , R ² in IV/R in V	m.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
						Calcd.	Found
1.	IVa	p-tolyl	Piperidino	107	62	12.61	12.55
2.	IVb	—do—	Morpholino	122	63	12.54	12.31
3.	IVc	—do—	Diethyl	125	61	13.08	13.00
4.	IVd	—do—	Dimethyl	133	65	14.33	14.20
5.	IVe	—do—	Bis(β-hydroxyethyl)	115	68	11.90	11.50
6.	IVf	p-methoxy phenyl	Piperidino	118	75	12.03	12.00
7.	IVg	—do—	Morpholino	90	73	11.42	11.35
8.	IVh	—do—	Diethyl	128	71	12.47	12.40
9.	IVi	—do—	Dimethyl	137	72	13.59	13.45
10.	Va	p-tolyl	Sulfanilamido	182	65	10.00	9.85
11.	Vb	—do—	4-Sulfanilamido-2,6-dimethoxy-pyrimidino	135	68	7.69	7.60
12.	Vc	—do—	5-Methyl-2-sulfanilamido-1,3,4-thiadiazolo	105	66	8.09	7.90
13.	Vd	—do—	4-Sulphanilamidopyrimidino	109	64	8.43	8.55
14.	Ve	—do—	N ¹ -Acetyl sulfanilamido	148	67	9.09	9.00
15.	Vf	—do—	4-Sulfanilamido-2,6-dimethyl-pyrimidino	192	68	16.00	16.15
16.	Vg	—do—	N ¹ -Guanyl sulfanilamido	98	72	18.14	18.05

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF 2-SUBSTITUTED 3-ARYL-QUINAZOLIN-4(3H)-ONES (IV AND V) ON FIVE BACTERIA

Sl. No.	Compound	Concentration in µg/ml	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)*				
			<i>S. lutea</i>	<i>B. megaterium</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>P. fluorescence</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	IVa	100	7.5	—	—	—	—
		200	8.0	—	—	—	—
2.	IVb	100	—	—	—	—	—
		200	—	—	—	—	—
3.	IVc	100	—	—	—	—	—
		200	—	—	—	—	—
4.	IVd	100	—	—	—	—	—
		200	—	—	—	—	—
5.	IVe	100	7.5	—	—	—	—
		200	8.5	—	—	—	—
6.	IVf	100	7.5	—	—	—	—
		200	8.0	—	—	—	—
7.	IVg	100	8.5	—	—	—	—
		200	9.5	—	—	—	—
8.	IVh	100	—	—	—	—	—
		200	—	—	—	—	—
9.	IVi	100	7.5	—	—	—	7.0
		200	9.5	—	—	—	8.5
10.	Va	100	7.5	—	—	—	7.0
		200	8.5	—	—	7.0	8.0
11.	Vb	100	—	—	—	—	—
		200	—	—	—	7.0	—
12.	Vc	100	—	—	—	—	—
		200	—	—	—	—	7.0
13.	Vd	100	7.5	—	—	—	7.5
		200	8.5	—	—	7.0	8.5
14.	Ve	100	7.5	—	7.0	—	—
		200	8.5	7.0	7.5	7.0	7.5
15.	Vf	100	—	—	7.0	—	—
		200	—	—	7.5	—	—
16.	Vg	100	—	—	7.5	—	—
		200	—	—	8.5	—	—

* Values include the diameter of paper disc (6 mm) also.

stirring. It was kept aside for few min and the resulting product (IV/V) was filtered, washed with cold water and dried. The compounds were recrystallized from alcohol.

Biological screening :

Antibacterial activity : Compounds IVa-i and Va-g were screened for their antibacterial activity by Vincent and Vincent¹¹ filter paper disc diffusion plate method. The gram +ve and gram -ve

bacteria employed for the tests were *Sarcina lutea*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas fluorescence*. The results are presented in Table 2.

Antifungal activity : The antifungal activity of all the compounds synthesised was determined by adopting the food poisoning technique¹². The fungi employed were *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Drechslera speciferum*, *Curvularia lunata* and *Alternaria alternata*. The results are discussed.

Results and Discussion

IR spectra of compounds IV exhibited an intense, sharp band around 1700 cm^{-1} due to C=O group in addition to the quinazoline nucleus at 1620 , 1595 and 1500 cm^{-1} , respectively¹³. Similarly, IR spectra of compounds V showed absorptions similar to those of IV except an additional absorption band around 1380 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of sulphonamido group¹⁴. The observed values of nitrogen analyses are in agreement with the calculated values. UV spectra of these compounds exhibited almost the same characteristics as those of other reported quinazolines⁶.

Perusal of Table 2 reveals that out of 9 compounds of type IV, compounds a, e, f and g were found to be active against *S. lutea* only, while compound i was active against *S. lutea* and *E. coli*. The other bacteria used were found insensitive to these compounds. The relatively higher activity of compounds IV f, g and i may be attributed to the 3-*p*-methoxyphenyl moiety. The 3-*p*-tolyl moiety is ineffective in inhibiting the growth of the bacteria. However, the antibacterial activity of compound IVa with 3-*p*-tolyl moiety may be attributed to the presence of piperidine moiety as this moiety along with 3-*p*-methoxyphenyl is also found to be effective in checking the growth of *S. lutea*. Comparatively higher toxicity of compound IVg than that of compound IVf reveals that the morpholino moiety is more bactericidal than piperidino. Compound IVi with N,N-dimethylamino moiety had a broad spectrum of activity as it caused the inhibition of both gram +ve (*S. lutea*) and gram -ve (*E. coli*) bacteria.

In general, compounds of type V were more bactericidal than those of type IV. However, the sensitivity of different bacteria varied with the compound. Compound Ve was active against all the bacteria tried, and compounds Va and Vd were active against *S. lutea*, *P. fluorescence* and *E. coli*. The rest of the compounds were selective in their activity. The wider spectrum of antibacterial activity of compound Ve may be attributed to N'-acetyl sulphonamido¹⁵ moiety. In view of the non-toxicity of tolyl group, the antibacterial activity of type V compounds can be assigned to the sulphonamido moiety. It is reported that various sulphonamides act through PAB mechanism¹⁶ in which the NH₂ group must be unsubstituted. The activity of some of the present compounds, inspite of their N⁴-substitution, suggests another mechanism of action¹⁷. The other possibility is that these N⁴-substituted aryl sulphonamides may be metabolised by the test organism resulting in the regeneration of the parent amine¹⁸.

The antifungal activity test of compounds of types IV and V revealed that these compounds were ineffective against *F. oxysporum* and *C. lunata*. However, *D. speciferum* and *A. alternata* showed some sensitivity towards some of the compounds. Compound IVa, IVd and Vd displayed marginal growth inhibition. Similarly, *D. speciferum* was also inhibited to the tune of 30% by compounds IVb and Vd. The present observations are in agreement with earlier reports³⁻⁷.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. Sisodia, Principal, University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Kakatiya University for facilities and encouragement. One of the authors (A.D.R) is grateful to I.C.M.R., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. B. M. GUPTA and S. K. KHAN, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1968, **7**, 61.
2. K. JOSEPH, *Ger. Pat.*, 1200307, 1965; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **63**, 12113a.
3. M. K. JAIN and K. S. NARAC, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 711.
4. H. TANIYAMA, B. YASUI, H. UCHIDA and Y. OKUDA, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1961, **81**, 431.
5. K. M. MURAVEVA, N. V. ARKHANGELSKAYA, M. N. SHCHUKINA, T. N. ZYKOVA and G. N. PERSHIN, *Khim. Farm. Zhur.*, 1968, **2**, 35; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **69**, 106658k.
6. A. H. ELSHERIF HOSNEY, A. M. ABDEL-AZEEM, M. ABDEL-KADER, ATEE and A. F. ABDEL-GHAFFAR, First Chemistry Conference, Faculty of Science, Assiut, Feb. 1979, p. 47 (Abstr.).
7. A. M. ABDEL-AZEEM and A. F. ABDEL-GHAFFAR, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1980, **42**, 79.
8. G. K. PANDEY and A. K. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 306.
9. J. MICHIO, I. MOSAVUKI, T. TAKASHI and T. SHIMAMOTO, *Japan Kakai*, 25 Mar. 1975, 7529, 575 (Cl. Co 7D), 14 Jul. 1973, Appl. 7378, 906; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **83**, 114464y.
10. P. A. PETUNIN and YU. V. KOZHEVNIKOV, *Khim. Geterotikl. Soedin.*, 1967, **Sb. 1**, 415; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **70**, 87739q.
11. J. C. VINCENT and H. W. VINCENT, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1944, **55**, 162.
12. Y. L. NENE and P. N. THAPLIYAL, *Naturwiss.*, 1965, **52**, 89.
13. H. CULBERTSON, J. C. DRUCE and B. E. CHRISTENSEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4834.
14. A. K. SEN GUPTA and A. ATRAY GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 297.
15. G. SHEPHERD ROBERT, "Medicinal Chemistry", Part-I, (Ed.) ALFRED BURGER, Wiley-Interscience, New York 1970.
16. E. H. NORTHEY, "The Sulfonamides and Allied Compounds", Reinhold, New York, 1948.
17. Y. MAEJIMA *Japan J. Bacteriol.*, 1952, **7**, 491.
18. K. CIANAPATHI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **12A**, 274.